

Characterisation of Pyrophosphato Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), and Fe(III)

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DETAILED studies on the composition and stability of the interaction products of pyrophosphate ions with various multivalent cations¹⁻⁵ have been made. In the present note we report the structure and ligand field parameters of pyrophosphato complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Fe(III).

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. quality and physical measurements were the same as reported earlier⁶.

The complexes were prepared by mixing the 0.2M solution of metal salts and disodium dihydrogen pyrophosphate keeping a slight excess of the latter in order to get a 1 : 2 (M : P) complex. The precipitates formed were filtered, washed several times with 50% alcohol and then dried in a desiccator over sulphuric acid.

- (i) Found : Cu, 13.11%, P₂O₇, 72.32%, Calc. for Na₂ [Cu(H₂P₂O₇)₂] H₂O : Cu, 13.25% ; P₂O₇, 72.57%.
- (ii) Found : Ni, 11.39% ; P₂O₇, 68.00%, Calc. for Na₂ [Ni(H₂P₂O₇)₂] (H₂O)₂ H₂O : Ni, 11.49%, P₂O₇, 68.14%.
- (iii) Found : Co, 11.45%, P₂O₇, 67.81% Calc. for Na₂ [Co(H₂P₂O₇)₂] (H₂O)₂, H₂O : Co, 11.53%, P₂O₇, 68.10%.
- (iv) Found : Fe, 11.41% ; P₂O₇, 71.35%, Calc. for Na[Fe(H₂P₂O₇)₂] (H₂O)₂] 2H₂O : Fe, 11.52% ; P₂O₇, 71.77%.

The molar conductance (0.001M aqueous solutions) of Fe(III) complex was found 90 mhos while that of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes were found 288 mhos which indicated the presence of two and three ions respectively.

Results and Discussion

The electronic spectrum of Co(II) complex gave a main band at 23809 cm⁻¹ (ν₃) and two shoulders at 18182 cm⁻¹ (ν₂) and 12300 cm⁻¹ (ν₁). The value of 10 Dq, B and β (Nephelauxetic ratio) was thus found to be 13705, cm⁻¹, 861 cm⁻¹ and 0.88 respectively. The spectrum of an aqueous solution of Ni(II) complex gave three absorption bands at ν₁ = 10000 cm⁻¹, ν₂ = 15700 cm⁻¹ and ν₃ = 26315 cm⁻¹ which is the characteristic feature of an octahedral structure. The value of 10 Dq, B and β was found to be 10000 cm⁻¹, 801 cm⁻¹ and 0.77 respectively. The ν₂/ν₁ of the complex was 1.57 which was also typical of six coordinate

geometry about Ni(II)⁷ One shoulder corresponding to 14000 cm⁻¹ was also obtained perhaps due to non-identical donor atoms indicating a slight geometrical distortion. The absorption spectra of the pale complex of iron gave a double peak at 12000 cm⁻¹ and bluish white complex of copper gave two bands at 13890 cm⁻¹ and 26000 cm⁻¹.

Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Fe(III) complexes were found paramagnetic with a magnetic moment of 1.87, 2.90, 5.00 and 5.90 B.M. respectively.

The main characteristic feature of the i.r. spectra was the shifting of ν (P-O-Na) at 1120 cm⁻¹ and ν(O-P-O) at 580 cm⁻¹ (Disodium dihydrogen phosphate) to 1080 cm⁻¹ and 540 cm⁻¹ (metal complexes) respectively which indicated the coordination of the metal through oxygen. The stretching bands due to water molecules at 3400 cm⁻¹ and 1640 cm⁻¹ and due to P-O-P at 940 cm⁻¹ were obtained in the spectra of all the complexes.

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Studies on the Succinimide Complexes of Pd(II), Au(III), Pt(IV), Ce(IV) and Th(IV)

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The simple and mixed ligand complexes of succinimide with common transition elements have been studied by several workers¹⁻⁵. In this note we deal with the composition, stability and structure of Pd(II), Au(III), Pt(IV), Ce(IV) and Th(IV) succinimide complexes.

Experimental

The chlorides of Pd(II), Au(III), Pt(V), K(I); nitrates of Ce(IV), Th(IV), K(I) and all other reagents used were of A.R. grade. The solution of PdCl₂ was prepared in 0.2M, HCl and of others in double distilled water.

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The complexes were prepared by mixing the reactants keeping a little excess of succinimide over the calculated amount in order to get the 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes and adjusting the $pH \approx 7.0$, 5.0 and 5.0 in the case of Pd(II), Th(IV) and Ce(IV) respectively with KOH. The resulting solutions were concentrated by slow evaporation at a temperature $\approx 65^\circ$ in a thermostat until the precipitates were formed, which were filtered off, washed several times with 50% alcohol and then dried over anhydrous sulfuric acid. However the complexes of Au(III) and Pd(IV) could not be isolated in the solid form.

(i) Found : Pd, 31.40% ; C, 28.40% ; H, 3.49%
Calc. for $[Pd(C_4H_4O_2N)_2(H_2O)_2]$: Pd, 31.44% ; C, 28.36% ; H, 3.54%.

(ii) Found : Ce, 37.50% ; C, 25.82% ; H, 2.60%
Calc. for $[Ce(C_4H_4O_2N)_2(OH)_2]$: Ce, 37.65% ; C, 25.79% ; H, 2.69%.

(iii) Found : Th, 50.18% ; C, 20.82% ; H, 2.10%
Calc. for $[Th(C_4H_4O_2N)_2(OH)_2]$: Th, 50.21% ; C, 20.77% ; H, 2.16%.

Palladium complex, on treatment with ammonia, or aliphatic amine gave white coloured crystalline complexes. The chemical analysis for the palladium carbon and hydrogen favoured the formulae of the type $[Pd(C_4H_4O_2N)_2(A)_2]$ where A=ammonia, methyl amine, ethyl amine, isopropyl amine or iso-butyl amine.

All these complexes were diamagnetic and of nonelectrolytic nature in nitrobenzene.

Results and Discussion

The pH titrations of the mixture of metal ion and succinimide in the ratios 1 : 0, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 with 0.1M KOH indicated a downward shift in pH from 1 : 0 to 1 : 1 in the case of Au(III) and Pt(IV) and from 1 : 0 to 1 : 1 to 1 : 2 in the case of other metals showing the liberation of hydrogen ions during the complex ion formation. Blank titration with succinimide had no effect upon the titration curves described above.

pK values as determined by potentiometric titration of 40 ml succinimide (0.025M) vs 0.084 KOH were found 9.45 and 9.70 in KCl and KNO_3 medium of 0.1M respectively.

Stability constants at $20^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ and keeping the ion, strength constant at 0.1 with KCl, in case of Pd(II), Au(III) and Pt(IV) and with KNO_3 in case of Ce(IV) and Th(IV) were determined by Bjerrum's method⁶. The value of $\log K$ (concentration constant) was found to be 17.4 ($\log k_1=9.1$, $\log k_2=8.3$), 18.9 ($\log k_1=10.2$, $\log k_2=8.7$), 14.6 ($\log k_1=7.5$, $\log k_2=7.1$), 6.2 and 8.4 in case of Pd(II), Ce(IV), Th(IV), Au(III) and Pt(IV) respectively. The accuracy of $\log K$ reported was 0.02. The \bar{n} values beyond ≈ 2.0 in case of Pd(II), Ce(IV) and Th(IV) and ≈ 1.0 in case of Au(III) and Pt(IV) could not be obtained with accuracy due to the onset of hydrolysis. The presence of polynuclear species could be neglected since the formation curves

(\bar{n} vs pA) determined from the ligand metal ratio of 5 : 1 and 6 : 1 were found identical.

The combining ratio was further confirmed by conductometric titration (20 ml of the ligand of conc. 0.03M and 0.05M in the cell) and amperometric titrations carried out at the plateau of succinimide i.e. -0.75 V. The main characteristic feature of the i.r spectra were the same as reported earlier⁵ with the difference of the bands associated with coordinated hydroxo group (1030 cm^{-1} and 600 cm^{-1}) and water molecules (820 cm^{-1} and 660 cm^{-1}).

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Preparation of (\pm)-Nitriles and (\pm)-Amides of Propesine and Butesine as Potential Drugs

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PROPESINE and butesine are known for their local anesthetic activity^{1,2}. They are also reported as antibacterial and antitubercular compounds^{3,4}. (\pm)- α -Aminonitriles are reported as compounds possessing insecticidal as well as CNS stimulant property^{5,6}.

In continuation of our previous work*, we prepared (\pm) nitriles of propesine and butesine as drug potentials for testing their antibacterial activity.

The (\pm) - α -Aminonitriles of the type.

have been synthesised, where

$\text{R}' = n - \text{C}_3\text{H}_7$ or $n - \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$ and

$\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; 4- $\text{CH}_3\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4$; 3- $\text{NO}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4$; $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O}$; 3- $\text{CH}_3\text{O} - 4 - \text{HO} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3$; 5- $\text{O}_2\text{N} - 3 - \text{CH}_3\text{O} - 4 - \text{HO} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_2$; 3,4- $(\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3$; 6-Br - 3,4- $(\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_2$; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CH}$; etc.

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